

UNPOP
METHODOLOGICAL
REPORT ON THE
DEVELOPMENT OF
THE SURVEY IN PT
AND IT (D4.2)

UNPOP 2025

UNPOP Methodological report on the development of the survey in PT and IT (D4.2)

This work is financed by Portuguese national funds through the FCT - Foundation for Science and Technology, I.P., under the project UNPOP “UNpacking POPulism: Comparing the formation of emotion narratives and their effects on political behaviour” (PTDC/CPO-CPO/3850/2020) and by FCT Funding (UIDP/50012/2020 and 2022.01525.CEECIND/CP1754/CT0005).

UNPOP Project website: <https://unpop.ces.uc.pt/en/>

Project coordination: Cristiano Gianolla and Lisete Mónico

Report authorship: Cristiano Gianolla and Lisete Mónico

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15066724](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15066724)

Publication in open access under a Creative Commons license CC BY 4.0

Centre for Social Studies, University of Coimbra, 21 March 2025

The UNPOP survey encompasses a range of scales to measure: social representation and emotions towards: people, elite and minorities; populist attitude, political emotions in relation to political realities and scenarios, political attitude and sociodemographic. The design of the survey was meticulously crafted to address potential sources of bias inherent in cross-cultural assessments. Initially, some of the scales were elaborated a direct translation from the English-language scales presented in the extant literature was conducted by two researchers, each an expert in their respective field. One researcher specialized in Political Science, while the other focused on Social Psychology. Special care was taken to preserve the original meaning of the items, while also ensuring their accessibility and understanding within the context of Portuguese culture. The two translations were then compared, and discrepancies were addressed until a consensus version of each item was achieved.

The survey's pilot test was conducted in Portugal in 2021, yielding 206 responses. Subsequent to this, two data collection campaigns were initiated in Portugal (2022, 906 responses; 2024, 1010 response) and one in Italy (2022, 890 responses). The final data collection in each country occurred during the electoral campaign for the parliamentary election, ten days prior to election day. The UNPOP survey obtained ethical clearance from the Ethics Commission of the Centre for Social Studies of the University of Coimbra in February 2021, both for Portuguese and Italian data collection.

The data gathering process involved the administration of online surveys. The pilot-testing data was collected via convenience sampling within the network of researchers, disseminated through their network channels. Participants from the second data collection in Portugal were recruited by psychology students within a specific course unit of Methods of Research at a Portuguese university. These students underwent training, which encompassed procedures regarding participant selection, conditions and instructions for applying questionnaires, and the ethical code. Each student was tasked with producing a final report that detailed the conditions under which data was collected, along with the inquiries posed by participants and their responses. Particular attention was paid to instructions and data collection procedures, data anonymity, and availability for feedback about the final results. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and each student provided a signature on an informed consent form. The third data collection in Portugal and the data collection in Italy was executed by a certified enterprise that collects data in several countries and are made freely available here. Participants were selected from a stratified sample based on sex, age, education, and geographical distribution.